

DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED HONEYCOMB STRUCTURES FOR OUT-OF-PLANE STIFFNESS AND ENERGY ABSORPTION

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ABSTRACT

Honeycomb structures, inspired by nature, are widely valued for their remarkable strength-to-weight ratios, making them indispensable in aerospace, automotive, and other engineering applications. This study explores the mechanical performance of functionally graded honeycomb structures with various thickness gradation configurations. Seven designs, including uniform and staged thickness variations, were analyzed through finite element method (FEM) simulations and validated with experimental testing to assess their behavior under compressive loading. The results demonstrate that incorporating thickness gradation significantly enhances mechanical properties compared to uniform designs. Staged configurations improved compressive strength, energy absorption, and crushing force efficiency, with the number and placement of thickness variations playing a critical role. While increasing the number of gradation stages refined stability and crushing force efficiency, it also resulted in trade-offs, such as reduced load-bearing capacity and energy absorption. Designs with strategically placed thin regions outperformed others in terms of energy dissipation and stability, highlighting their suitability for applications requiring controlled deformation and impact resistance. This study provides valuable insights into the design and optimization of functionally graded honeycomb structures, offering a pathway for developing lightweight, high-performance materials tailored to specific engineering needs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Honeycomb structures, inspired by the natural design of beehives, have long been recognized for their outstanding combination of low density and high stiffness [1], making them ideal for a range of applications across industries such as aerospace [2], automotive [3], architecture [4], and biomedicine [5]. The unique cellular configuration of honeycombs offers exceptional strength and energy absorption [6-9], particularly in sandwich composite designs, which are widely used in critical structures where weight reduction and impact resistance are paramount [10, 11]. Under out-of-plane loads, honeycombs exhibit high stiffness due to axial extension or compression of their cell walls, which provide structural support [12]. However, the in-plane stiffness of honeycomb structures remains relatively low, primarily due to the bending stresses arising from the distinct geometry of the cells [13].

Recent advancements in honeycomb design have sought to optimize their mechanical properties, particularly to enhance the in-plane behavior of these materials. This has led to efforts to adjust the geometry of honeycomb cells, including the angles of hexagonal cells, to create tailored materials suited for specific applications. One notable development in this field involves the integration of auxetic materials—materials that exhibit a negative Poisson's ratio—into traditional honeycomb structures [14, 15]. These auxetic designs, such as hybrid honeycombs with split vertical struts, have been shown to significantly improve compressive strength, energy absorption, and the overall deformation patterns of honeycombs, which are crucial for controlled collapse and maintaining structural integrity in dynamic load conditions [16].

Alongside these geometric optimizations, the concept of functionally graded materials (FGMs) has emerged as a promising approach to enhance honeycomb performance. FGMs allow for a gradual variation in material properties across the structure, resulting in improved strength, durability, and environmental resistance [17]. This gradual change in properties, unlike traditional composites that feature abrupt transitions, enables the design of more efficient structures with tailored mechanical characteristics, such as modulus, density, and thermal conductivity [18-20]. Initially developed for aerospace applications requiring efficient thermal barriers, FGMs have since expanded into sectors such as biomedical, chemical, nuclear, and energy engineering, where high-performance materials are critical [21].

Building on these advancements, recent research has explored functionally graded honeycomb structures, which incorporate varying geometries of unit cells across their panels to achieve tailored mechanical properties. By adjusting the geometries, honeycomb structures can exhibit enhanced stiffness-to-weight ratios, which is particularly beneficial for lightweight mechanical and aerospace applications. The introduction of FGMs into these gradient honeycombs has demonstrated improvements in overall stiffness, shear modulus, and bending performance, further enhancing the suitability of these structures for applications that demand precise mechanical performance and optimized strength-to-weight ratios [22-24].

In this study, we focus on the design and manufacturing of functionally graded honeycomb structures with linear thickness variations in the out-of-plane direction in each stage. Specifically, seven configurations are considered:

1. Uniform average thickness
2. A single-stage thick-thin variation
3. A double-stage thick-thin-thick variation
4. A double-stage thin-thick-thin variation
5. A triple-stage thin-thick-thin-thick variation
6. A quadruple-stage thin-thick-thin-thick-thin variation
7. A quadruple-stage thick-thin-thick-thin-thick variation

To validate these designs, finite element method (FEM) simulations were performed to predict mechanical performance under out-of-plane compressive loading. Experimental tests using a universal testing machine (UTM) were carried out to validate these simulations and characterize key mechanical properties, including stiffness, densification displacement, mean crushing force, and energy absorption capacity. This study aims to deepen the understanding of functionally graded honeycombs and their potential applications in high-performance scenarios, such as in aerospace, automotive, and packaging industries, where tailored mechanical responses are essential for optimized structural performance.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Esun PLA+ filaments which are known for their combination of low melting point and high strength were used in this study for printing functionally graded honeycomb structures. The dog-bone shaped tensile test specimens, 165 mm in length and 19 mm in width, were produced using Bambu Lab P1S 3D printer. The tensile properties of the filaments were obtained by tensile tests using a UTM equipped with a 50 kN load cell according to ASTM D638 standard. The stress strain data of the filaments under tensile loading are depicted in Figure 1.

All samples were printed with 100% infill value as it ensures uniform mechanical properties across the material. This helps the object retain its shape and structural integrity especially under prolonged applied loads. The recommended nozzle temperature for Esun PLA+ filament is reported to be between 210-230 °C, therefore, 220 °C was selected for 3D printing. The installed nozzle has 0.4 mm extrusion diameter for finer resolution of samples. Bed temperature of 50 °C provided adequate adhesion and minimized warping effects for the samples. Additionally, the printing speed of 100 mm/min was found to be sufficient for desirable quality of the samples.

Figure 1: Esun PLA+ material experimental tensile stress-strain curve and testing apparatus.

2.2 Design and Fabrication of Graded Honeycomb Structures

The unit cell used in this study is shown in Figure 2 where parameters L , H , t_1 , t_2 , t_{avg} , and θ represent the side length, unit cell height, thickness of the thin section, thickness of the thick section, average thickness where $t_{avg} = (t_1 + t_2)/2$, and interior angle of the unit cell, respectively. The geometrical dimensions of the honeycomb unit cells are as follows: the side length L is 15 mm, the unit cell height H is 30 mm, the thickness t_1 is 0.5 mm, t_2 is 1.5 mm, t_{avg} is 1 mm, and the interior angle θ is 30°. For this study, the average thickness of 1 mm was maintained across all samples to ensure equal mass, regardless of variations in the design pattern. This approach eliminates the need to use mass-normalized, specific values for comparison. A double-stage unit cell is shown in Figure 2, clarifying the average thickness concept for tapered configurations.

Figure 2: An illustration of a double-stage unit cell: a) Top view, b) side view of a single cell wall, and c) isometric view of the unit cell.

Model designs of honeycomb unit cells were developed using CATIA V5 software. The models were generated with a symmetric design approach, where the unit cells are arranged radially around a central origin point, leading to an axisymmetric design. This circular distribution facilitates compression testing by allowing the samples to be directly tested without the need for additional plates. Moreover, this design minimizes the area occupied by the samples, allowing them to fit efficiently within the standard circular plates of the UTM machine.

A systematic approach was adopted for naming different honeycomb configurations based on their thickness variations. The naming convention uses a combination of letters and numbers to represent the configuration type, ensuring clarity and brevity. The prefix H was used for all structures, indicating the honeycomb geometry. Depending on the variations in the thickness, U stands for uniform thickness whereas SS, DS, TS, and QS refer to linear thickness variations in a single stage, a double stage, a triple stage, and a quadruple stage in an alternating thinning and thickening sense. Then, numeric characters were used in between to describe the thickness values at the top face of honeycombs getting in contact with the load applying platen in mm.

This design scheme leads to only one configuration in honeycombs with an odd number of stages since having a thin or thick cell wall at the top face generates the same configuration, upside down. However, for an even number of stages, two different configurations arise and the top face thickness becomes important. For example, H-0.5SS stands for a single stage honeycomb where the thickness linearly varies between 0.5 and 1.5 mm from top to bottom. On the other hand, H-1.5QS denotes a sample with four stages where in each sample the thickness varies between 0.5 and 1.5 mm with the thickness at the top face is 1.5 mm. To maintain consistency, the codes and their corresponding configurations have been documented in Table 1. Furthermore, computer aided designs (CAD) of the corresponding configurations are depicted in Figure 3.

Configuration Description	Honeycomb
Uniform thickness of 1 mm	H-1U
Single stage variation (0.5 mm to 1.5 mm)	H-0.5SS
Double stage with 1.5 mm thickness at the top face	H-1.5DS
Double stage with 0.5 mm thickness at the top face	H-0.5DS
Triple stage with 0.5 mm thickness at the top face	H-0.5TS
Quadruple stage with 1.5 mm thickness at the top face	H-1.5QS
Quadruple stage with 0.5 mm thickness at the top face	H-0.5QS

Table 1: Configuration descriptions and their corresponding codes.

2.3 Energy Absorption Characteristics

The energy absorption characteristics of cellular structures are primarily described using six key indices: densification displacement (x_d), mean crushing force (F_m), peak force (F_{max}), crushing force efficiency (e_f), and energy absorption (EA). Among these, the most prominent parameters are x_d and F_m . The expressions of these parameters are obtained based on the energy absorption efficiency approach as noted by Li et al. [25] and detailed below.

The energy absorption efficiency $\eta(x)$ is defined as:

$$\eta(x) = \frac{1}{F(x)H} \int_{x_y}^x F(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} \quad (1)$$

where $F(x)$ represents the compressive force, H is the specimen height, and x_y denotes the displacement value at the end of the linear region. The densification displacement corresponds to the displacement at which $\eta(x)$ achieves its maximum value, determined by:

$$\left. \frac{d\eta(x)}{dx} \right|_{x=x_d} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The peak force is the maximum compressive force observed until densification begins. The mean crushing force, a critical parameter reflecting the energy absorption capability of the structure in the plateau phase, is then calculated as follows:

$$F_m = \frac{\int_{x_y}^{x_d} F(\bar{x}) d\bar{x}}{x_d - x_y} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: Computer aided drawing designs of functionally graded honeycomb lattice structures:
a) H-1U, b) H-0.5SS, c) H-0.5DS, d) H-1.5DS, e) H-0.5TS, f) H-0.5QS, and g) H-1.5QS.

Energy absorption represents the total energy absorbed by the cellular structure during compression and is determined as the area under the force-displacement curve:

$$EA = \int_0^{x_d} F(\bar{x}) d\bar{x} \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, the crushing force efficiency is the ratio of the mean crushing force to the peak force:

$$e_f = \frac{F_m}{F_{max}} \quad (5)$$

Finally, stiffness is a material or structure's fundamental resistance to elastic deformation when a force is applied. It is quantitatively measured as the ratio of force to displacement $k = F/\delta$, typically in N/m. In our study, it specifically refers to the initial out-of-plane compressive stiffness of honeycomb structures, where a balance of stiffness and controlled deformation is key for effective energy absorption in impact applications.

2.4 Finite Element Analysis

ABAQUS commercial software was employed to analyze the mechanical behavior of honeycomb structures under compression loading and validate experimental findings. To perform the simulations, a dynamic-explicit solver with smooth loading was selected, which is suitable for quasi-static loading conditions. A total time step of 0.05 s was considered to expedite the simulations while retaining quasi-static conditions. To confirm the validity of the quasi-static analysis conducted using the dynamic-explicit solver, the kinetic energy values must be negligible compared to the internal energy values [26]. This verification is illustrated in Figure 4 which confirms the accuracy of the simulation model.

A general contact approach was used to model interactions between the structural components, with a friction coefficient of 0.2. The lower surface was fixed while the upper surface underwent axial displacement loading to replicate the boundary conditions of the experimental tests. The structure was meshed using C3D8R elements, and a mesh size of 0.3 mm was used.

Figure 4: Internal and kinetic energies for H-1U under out-of-plane FEM compression test.

2.5 Experimental Characterization

Compression testing of physical samples were carried out by Shimadzu AGS-X UTM with a 50 kN load cell. Samples were subjected to compression tests with a persistent displacement rate of 3 mm/min until 80% strain is achieved for each model. At least three samples were tested according to ASTM C365 guidelines, and the obtained force-displacement data were utilized to calculate mechanical properties including peak force, densification displacement, energy absorption, mean crushing force, and crushing force efficiency.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As an illustrative case, the experimental results obtained from three different samples and the finite element analysis results of H-1U samples are shown in Figure 5 where EXP stands for the experimental data. Based on the results presented in Figure 5, the printing quality among three different samples is quite similar, evinced from the force-displacement behavior of the samples showing almost identical results until around 6 mm, beyond which the impurities start altering the behavior. Furthermore, the FEM and experimental results are in close agreement, indicating the accuracy of the FEM simulations.

Figure 5: Experimental and numerical (FEM) out-of-plane force-displacement curves for H-1U.

A MATLAB code which utilizes the force displacement curves as inputs was developed to calculate the important performance metrics pertinent to mechanical characteristics of honeycomb structures in the out-of-plane direction such as densification displacement, peak force, mean crushing force, crushing force efficiency, and energy absorption. The force-displacement curves for FEM and experimental tests are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. The performance metrics obtained via the developed MATLAB code are tabulated in Table 2. The tabulated results provide a comprehensive overview of the mechanical performance of seven distinct honeycomb configurations; each designed with variations in out-of-plane thickness. By analyzing key metrics such as stiffness, densification displacement, mean crushing force, and energy absorption, one can discern clear trends and identify optimal designs for specific applications.

Regarding initial deformation behavior, the uniform H-1U configuration stands out with the longest linear region (0.94 ± 0.01 mm), indicating its superior ability to withstand elastic deformation before permanent yielding. In contrast, designs like H-0.5SS, H-0.5DS, and H-0.5TS, characterized by thinner top sections or a single-stage linear variation, exhibit significantly lower linear regions, suggesting they begin to deform plastically much earlier. This trade-off implies that while H-1U is more resilient to initial deformation, the graded designs might be more suitable for applications where controlled, early initiated plastic deformation is a desired mechanism for protection systems.

When considering the structure's capacity for energy absorption through deformation, the densification displacement becomes crucial. Here, H-0.5TS configuration excels, demonstrating the highest densification displacement (23.99 ± 0.31 mm). This indicates that the triple-stage design with a thin top face can effectively absorb energy over a larger deformation range before fully compacting. Similarly, H-0.5QS and H-0.5SS also show high densification displacements, positioning these graded structures as superior choices for impact protection and scenarios requiring prolonged energy dissipation. Conversely, H-1.5DS, which features a thick top face, exhibits the lowest densification displacement, suggesting a more rapid compaction and thus a smaller effective energy absorption range.

In terms of load-carrying capacity and energy absorption efficiency, the peak force, mean crushing force, and crushing force efficiency metrics offer valuable insights. H-0.5TS consistently leads in both peak force (22.72 ± 2.98 kN) and mean crushing force (11.90 ± 0.28 kN), highlighting its robust load-bearing capacity and effective energy absorption during the crushing phase. While H-0.5TS shows strong performance, H-0.5DS distinguishes itself with the highest crushing force efficiency ($66.87 \pm 5.03\%$). This high efficiency suggests a very stable and consistent crushing behavior after the initial peak load, which is highly beneficial for predictable energy dissipation in crashworthiness applications.

In contrast, the uniform H-1U and the thicker top-faced H-1.5DS and H-1.5QS configurations generally exhibit lower crushing force efficiencies, indicating a more abrupt force drop after the peak load.

The ultimate measure of a structure's impact resistance is its total energy absorption capacity. The results overwhelmingly favor the graded designs, with H-0.5TS absorbing a remarkable 281.98 ± 10.64 J of energy, significantly outperforming all other configurations. H-0.5QS and H-0.5SS also demonstrate excellent energy absorption capabilities, reinforcing the benefits of functional grading for impact protection. The H-1.5DS, with its thicker top face, shows the lowest energy absorption, underscoring that certain grading strategies are more effective for maximizing energy dissipation.

Finally, regarding stiffness, which reflects the structure's resistance to initial elastic deformation, H-1.5DS exhibits the highest value (25.60 ± 1.33 N/m). The uniform H-1U also demonstrates good stiffness. While the graded designs like H-0.5TS and H-0.5QS show comparable stiffness values, those with thinner top faces (H-0.5SS and H-0.5DS) tend to be slightly less stiff. This suggests that for applications demanding maximum initial rigidity, configurations with uniform thickness or thicker starting layers might be marginally preferable, though the differences in stiffness among most graded samples are not as dramatic as the differences in energy absorption.

Figure 6: Force-displacement curves of honeycomb samples from FEM analyses.

Sample	x_y (mm)	x_d (mm)	F_{max} (kN)	F_m (kN)	e_f (%)	EA (J)	K (kN/mm)
H-1U	0.94 ± 0.01	21.01 ± 0.88	19.79 ± 0.23	7.80 ± 0.23	39.41 ± 1.39	167.02 ± 10.98	24.38 ± 0.26
H-0.5SS	0.47 ± 0.02	22.13 ± 0.44	17.62 ± 2.00	9.88 ± 0.39	56.42 ± 4.48	216.14 ± 12.97	20.20 ± 1.67
H-0.5DS	0.54 ± 0.03	20.99 ± 0.43	14.15 ± 1.18	9.42 ± 0.11	66.87 ± 5.03	195.72 ± 4.41	21.93 ± 0.77
H-1.5DS	0.76 ± 0.02	17.81 ± 0.29	15.82 ± 0.80	7.30 ± 0.39	46.27 ± 4.42	130.81 ± 7.97	25.60 ± 1.33
H-0.5TS	0.58 ± 0.00	23.99 ± 0.31	22.72 ± 2.98	11.90 ± 0.28	52.74 ± 5.67	281.98 ± 10.64	23.09 ± 1.73
H-0.5QS	0.70 ± 0.02	23.16 ± 0.38	17.36 ± 2.95	10.41 ± 0.20	60.96 ± 8.58	238.78 ± 8.53	23.05 ± 1.02
H-1.5QS	0.70 ± 0.04	21.97 ± 0.20	19.29 ± 2.36	8.94 ± 0.46	46.54 ± 3.33	194.78 ± 11.96	23.45 ± 2.22

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the honeycomb samples.

Figure 7: Experimental force-displacement curves of honeycomb samples.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study thoroughly investigated the compressive behavior of various honeycomb structures, comparing uniform (H-1U) and functionally graded designs. The experimental and FEM simulation results showed very good agreement, validating the simulation approach adopted. Through a user-friendly MATLAB script, key performance metrics including compressive force, mean crushing force, crushing force efficiency, energy absorption, densification displacement, and stiffness were evaluated.

The results demonstrate that functionally graded honeycomb structures offer significant advantages over uniform designs, particularly in energy absorption capacity and crushing force efficiency. The triple-stage configuration (H-0.5TS), characterized by a thin top face, consistently emerged as the superior design for applications demanding high impact resistance and effective energy dissipation, absorbing a remarkable 281.98 ± 10.64 J of energy. While uniform designs like H-1U showed longer elastic region (resilience to initial elastic deformation) and H-1.5DS exhibited the highest stiffness, the overall gains in energy absorption and controlled crushing behavior observed in graded structures like H-0.5QS and H-0.5SS were substantial.

In conclusion, although certain graded designs may demonstrate earlier permanent deformation or exhibit slightly reduced initial stiffness, their enhanced capacity for energy dissipation—achieved through controlled deformation and prolonged energy absorption—renders them highly advantageous. These results underscore the potential of functionally graded structures to enable tailored mechanical responses, offering significant promise for high-performance applications in impact-critical sectors such as aerospace and automotive engineering.

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